

MOBILE TECHNOLOGICAL METHODS OF SAFETY MANAGEMENT IN SURFACE MINING

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Abstract: Improving the quality of equipment training for operators of complex equipment is an important task improving safety in mining and eliminating equipment-related injuries. one of the main responsibilities for This is a proper car inspection. Traditional miner safety training involves the use of hard copy documentation and video instructions. However, modern mobile and computer technologies offer great opportunities to improve the learning process. In this study, we use a 360-degree camera, open source platform WordPress™ and Unity3D software to help create safety training materials and tools to help trainees better understand pre-shift safety machine inspections. The computer-based safety training developed in this study was field-tested.

Keywords: Complex equipment operators, teaching safety rules, 360 degree image/video, virtual reality, the limit of distance, boundary field image.

Introduction

Safe provision of workplaces is one of the main objectives of mining for companies and all people working in mines. In addition to machine control, operators of complex technological equipment have another crucial task: to properly inspect the car. failure to perform a A proper check of the car before the shift can lead to a domino effect, lead to more serious problems or incidents. In transfer Task-training for CEOs, Mine Safety Guidelines should be considered. To help reduce deaths, injuries and illnesses in mines assists mine operators by developing and implementing and enforcing safety and health regulations. Internet-based training (IBT); for example, it could be travel time is reduced, costs are reduced, materials can be easily revised and renewed, high efficiency can be achieved and so on. All these factors are present and valuable in the process of training personnel in the mining industry. Some researchers have developed non-immersive learning prototypes that can only run on standard personal computers. A computer workstation is a suitable platform for this virtual tours guided by the participants themselves. On the one hand, non-

immersive virtual reality computer systems Does not provide full access to the VR world. On the other hand handheld, the systems are an affordable option for high-fidelity design, teaching and learning applications. commented on the development of virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) in the field of construction safety. They are concluded that their research is not limited to construction industry and future research should incorporate AR/VR for safety personnel training in other fields. As another part of this study, full immersion in the world of VR the project can be achieved through the use of virtual reality applications and VR headsets. Improvements allow mine safety and health practices to grow, in the future I will discuss several approaches to virtual reality training. In mining, VR environments are about enabling for mine workers to experience various activities and processes This can be expected in their daily activities. From this point of view, it's a one-day activity that every heavy equipment operator can do waiting to be done is to check the car before the shift.

The advancement of technology in the virtual world

For the first time in managing sophisticated technology, this research has chosen a suitable camera for 360-degree photography. graded images and videos. There are many 360 degrees Cameras currently available in the market. GoPro Fusion (Picture 1), is one such camera that is capable of performing the required tasks by this study and is a convenient model to use. The camera consists of two 180-degree lenses, one on the front and one on the back camera side. Lenses capture two images at the same time or Two videos that can be stitched together to create a single 360-degree image or video. The camera captures 18-megapixel still images and 5.2K videos. Several types of head-mounted displays are available As the only headset for VR systems. Some examples of singularity headsets Oculus Rift, HTC VIVE, Oculus Quest, etc. This research the project used Oculus Rift Consumer Version 1 (CV 1) as the hardware for the VR system. This HMD has two joysticks and two external sensors. Joysticks are used to control their position manipulation of objects in the world of virtual reality. Sensors track location and translate user movements into VR. There are several Requirements proposed by Oculus to provide Oculus Rift CV 1 works properly on a computer or laptop. The minimum requirement is this Intel i3-6100 processor and NVIDIA GTX 1050 Ti or higher range graphics card. Otelbayev Azizbek laptop used in this project was Acer Nitro3. This laptop Compatible with Oculus Rift and therefore virtual reality. The laptop is a low-end gaming laptop powered by NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1050ti graphics card and Intel Core i5-8300H

processor. So this laptop meets the minimum requirements as well as has the manufacturer's "Oculus Ready" label.

Picture 1. A camera that can show 360 degrees. (GoPro Fusion).

With this camera, Azizbek managed to remotely receive the images taken from the camera directly into the computer's memory by transmitting computer signals. This is very important in mining, because it helps to ensure safety in the mine, and first of all, it helps to save people's lives. We can see a full 360-degree view of the mine from a distance. Software used in the creation, editing and stages The development of educational content consisted of: This program is free and allows you to display spherical images and videos, adjust colors, load content from a folder or directly from it. install the camera and set the image stabilization. This study chose WordPress, an open source content management system, to create a PC-based task-training application. 3D Open source content management systems like WordPress, has become a very popular and widely used set of tools for creating, modifying, editing and publishing web-based content. systems. Unity3D is free software and game development instrument. Unity3D has a variety of free and paid assets. These are possible help develop applications for desktop, web or mobile devices. The version of Unity3D used to create a VR application in this study it was 2022. In addition, educational materials are provided with image, sound, and video editing. The first goal of training is related to getting around, one of the most important functions of all heavy equipment operators. It is necessary to check during the inspection various machine parts, not only help to ensure safety the safety of the operator as well as other people working mining site. Here are some machine parts to check during this process tires, fire extinguishing system, fire extinguishers, leaks, mechanical defects, etc. The second objective of the training involves the preoperative cabin was and serves as part of the pre-shift inspection provide a safe cabin environment. For example, during the inspection of the cabin, the

operator must check the operation of the seat belts, horn, steering, brake systems, window and other parts of the cabin. safe operation of the machine. The third main objective focuses on proper working procedures start-up and shutdown, as well as for emergency events that must be monitored in certain situations.

Results and discussion

After the previously described process of gathering 360 degrees images, 360-degree videos and 2D images, these were the materials Included in computer-based task-training software and VR app. These materials are an important part of the internship the ability to interact with the learning process. However, videos and there may also be images taken with a 360-degree camera used separately and independently from the developed software. For example, such 360-degree images and videos can be launched any player that fits this type of composition. One Media Players that support 360-degree content are GoPro VR player. It is also possible to view 360-degree content by using it Oculus Rift HMD without including such materials VR application. However, the process of using images one by one can be significantly slower because a person has to change manually picture or video and add new ones.

Conclusions

I have done a lot of research on computer-based task training and viewing virtual reality images. A (VR) application developed through this research provides education for heavy equipment operators providing a better understanding the importance of procedures and pre-shift inspections. This achieved through interactive and structured lessons. Educational materials, including 360-degree images and videos, 2D images and audio data were generated for seven cars. A graphical user interface for computer-based task training. software developed and adapted for use on personal computers and mobile devices. A training template was created to develop a new training course with AutoCad3D. It was a virtual reality app designed for use on desktop computers or the Oculus Rift CV 1 head mounted display. The effectiveness of this technology has been supported with respect to training traditional methods should be the target of future research. Although mine personnel have been involved in every step of the development and mine testing of this project/system, intending to conduct more scientific research on its utility and usefulness. satisfaction with the developed system and calculation of income return on investment. In addition, familiarization with modern photography and videography equipment to collect more advanced images and videos should be

considered. Focus on editing such materials reach the semi-professional level and include turns them into developed software.

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